

New records and synonymy in Xyphosiini and Tephritini (Diptera Tephritidae Tephritinae) from the Far East of Russia

Новые находки и синонимия Хурфосиини и Тэфритини (Diptera Tephritidae Tephritinae) Дальнего Востока России

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КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: Diptera, мухи, мухи-пестрокрылки, Tephritidae, Tephritini, Xyphosiini, Россия, Дальний Восток, систематика, фауна.

ABSTRACT. Diagnosis of the Xyphosiini is redefined; the tribe includes *Ictericica* Lw., *Ictericodes* Hering, and *Xyphosia* R.-D. *Merzomyia* Korneyev, nom.n., is proposed as a replacement name for *Westermannia* Lioy. *Merzomyia westermanni* (Meigen, 1826) comb.n., *M. licenti* (Chen in: Zia et Chen, 1938) comb.n. and *M. mongolica* (Korneyev, 1990) comb.n. are included in this genus *Tephritis heringi* Korneyev, nom.n., is a replacement name for *Tephritis multiguttata* Hering, 1953, junior secondary homonym of *Tephritis multiguttata* (Becker, 1913) (= *Euribia multiguttata* Becker, 1913). The following synonymy is established: *Dioxya bidentis* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830) = *Paroxyna cheni* Zia, 1937, syn.n., *Campiglossa luxorientis* (Hering, 1940) = *Paroxyna melanochoa* Hering, 1941, syn.n., *Tephritis okera* (Shinji, 1940) = *Tephritis ismene* Hering, 1953, syn.n., non Rondani, 1871, *Tephritis sonchina* Hering, 1937 = *T. mandschurica* Hering, 1953, syn.n. *Trupanea guttistella* Hering, 1951 = *Trupanea collina* Ito, 1984, syn.n. The following species are recorded from the Far East Russia for the first time: *Ictericodes depuncta* (Hering), comb.n. (= *Ictericica depuncta*, *Acinia depuncta* auctt.), *Tephritis cometa cingulata* Hering, *T. jocaste* Hering, *T. sonchina* Hering, *Trupanea convergens* Hering, *Tephritis pterostigma* Hering, *Trupanea guttistella* Hering, *Tephritis okera* (Shinji), *T. majuscula* Hering et Ito, *Tephritis hyosciami* (L.). *Gonioxya atrata* Wang is placed to *Homoeotricha atrata* (Wang) comb.n.

Xyphosia R.-D. Родовое название *Merzomyia* предложено как замещающее для *Westermannia* Lioy. Род включает *Merzomyia westermanni* (Meigen, 1826) comb.n., *M. licenti* (Chen in: Zia et Chen, 1938) comb.n. и *M. mongolica* (Korneyev, 1990) comb.n. *Tephritis heringi* Korneyev, nom.n. — замещающее название для *Tephritis multiguttata* Hering, 1953, non *Euribia multiguttata* Becker, 1913. Установлена синонимия: *Dioxya bidentis* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830) = *Paroxyna cheni* Zia, 1937, syn.n., *Campiglossa luxorientis* (Hering, 1940) = *Paroxyna melanochoa* Hering, 1941, syn.n., *Tephritis okera* (Shinji, 1940) = *Tephritis ismene* Hering, 1953, syn.n., *Tephritis sonchina* Hering, 1937 = *T. mandschurica* Hering, 1953, syn.n., *Trupanea guttistella* Hering, 1951 = *Trupanea collina* Ito, 1984, syn.n. Впервые для района исследований указываются *Ictericodes depuncta* (Hering), comb.n. (= *Ictericica depuncta*, = *Acinia depuncta* auctt.), *Tephritis cometa cingulata* Hering, *T. jocaste* Chen, *T. sonchina* Hering, *Trupanea convergens* Hering, *Tephritis pterostigma* Hering, *Trupanea guttistella* Hering, *Tephritis okera* (Shinji), *T. majuscula* Hering et Ito, *Tephritis hyosciami* (L.). *Homoeotricha atrata* (Wang) comb.n. перемещена из рода *Gonioxya*.

Introduction

The main taxonomic and faunistic works dealing with Tephritinae of the Russian Far East were referred to in my previous papers [Korneyev, 1986, 1987, 1990]. Also, the Palaearctic species of the genus *Urophora* (tribe Myopitini) have been revised by Korneyev and White [1991, 1992, 1993].

When treating material from the collections of Zoological Institute (St.-Petersburg), of Zoologi-

РЕЗЮМЕ. Показано, что триба Хурфосиини включает *Ictericica* Lw., *Ictericodes* Hering, и

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cal Museum of the Moscow University and of Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology (Kiev), and preparing a chapter of Dipteran volume for "The Keys for Identification to Insects of the Soviet Far East", several species of the subfamily Tephritinae were added to the list of species known already from this region.

The following acronyms are used for the institutions where the collections are located:

DEI — Project Entomologie (Deutsches Entomologisches Institut), Eberswalde-Finow; SIZK — Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kiev; NHML — Natural History Museum, London (formerly British Museum (Natural History)); UOP — University of Osaka Prefecture, ZISP — Zoological Institute, Russian Academy of Sciences, St.-Petersburg; ZMUM — Zoological Museum of the Moscow University.

Subfamily Tephritinae

Tribe Xyphosiini Hendel, 1927

REMARKS. Hendel [1927] originally included in the Xyphosiini, besides *Xyphosia* R.-D., also *Acinia* R.-D. (now assigned to Tephritini), and *Ictericodes* Lw. The Palearctic species placed in the latter genus are now treated under *Ictericodes* Hering and *Merzomyia* Korneyev, nom.n. (see below). The New World tribe Acrotaeniini [Foote et al., 1993] apparently is closely related.

Ictericodes is the only Palearctic genus closely related to *Xyphosia*. Another genus obviously belonging here is *Ictericodes* Loew (see below). The diagnosis of Xyphosiini must be redefined as follows.

DIAGNOSIS. Anterior and posterior orbital bristles of same colour (plesiomorphy). Outside Tephritinae, in Tephritinae: Terelliini, in the genera, related to *Jamesomyia* Quisenberry and *Hypenidium* Loew, and in Aciurini posterior **or** is black to light yellow, as the anterior one, whereas in the remaining Tephritinae **p or** is white (except in Myopitini having only one **or**).

All head and body bristles and setae are yellow (apomorphy). Most Tephritidae have bristles black to dark brown, except in *Acidoxantha* Hendel (Trypetinae) and in some species of *Terellia* R.-D. and *Acinia* R.-D. In Xyphosiini and Acrotaeniini *all* bristles are yellow, neither black, nor white. It can be either a synapomorphy of Xyphosiini + Acrotaeniini, or a homoplasy.

Scapular bristles slightly longer than mesonotal setae. In most Tephritidae, other than Tephritinae (except *Plioreocepta* Korneyev, *Cephalophysa* Hering, and *Malica* Richter) scapular bristles are large, 2-5 times longer than other mesonotal setae; this state is presumed plesiomorphic; in *Plioreocepta*, Tephritinae: Terelliini, Xyphosiini, Acrotaeniini, Myopitini, and in the genera related to *Jamesomyia*, they are only 1.5 times longer than setae, so this character is presumed apomorphic. Furthermore, in Oedaspidini, Eutretini, Schistopterini and Tephritini there is no distinctive scapular bristles at all, and it is hypothesized to be an advanced state comparing to Xyphosiini and allied taxa. For the genera of Xyphosiini this character is believed to be a symplesiomorphy.

Vein R_{4+5} setulose below (and usually above) to **RM** (plesiomorphic). Outside Tephritinae there is R_{4+5} setulose below and above in Blepharoneurinae, Acanthonevrinae, Trypetinae: Gastrozonini, and in some other taxa, so this state is presumed to be plesiomorphic. Inside Tephritinae, this character state is found in all Xyphosiini, Acrotaeniini, Cecidocharini, *Acinia*, *Dithryca* Rondani, *Paracantha* Loew, *Pseudacinia*, *Platensina* Bezzi, some *Tephritis* Latreille and *Trupanea* Schrank. It is absent in many non-related or remote genera of Tephritinae, including all Terelliini. In the case of Terelliini it is the synapomorphy of the tribe, but the weight of this character is extremely low due to numerous homoplasies.

Wing pattern reticulate (apomorphy). Most Tephritidae beyond Tephritinae have striate or so-called "aciuroid" type of wing pattern, and the reticulate type of pattern found in few genera of Acanthonevrinae and other subfamilies is apparently derived of the other two types. In the Terelliini and Acrotaeniini, as well as in Myopitini and Cecidocharini wing pattern is striate, whereas in Oedaspidini, Tephrellini and genera, allied to *Jamesomyia* the reticulate pattern is found in few species and is considered to appear independently. The reticulate pattern is widespread in the Eutretini/Schistopterini/Tephritini complex. The latter taxa are the most advanced clade of Tephritinae that might be a derivative of the Xyphosiini, but not its ancestral group. Therefore, the reticulate pattern is considered here to be a synapomorphy of *Xyphosia* R.-D., *Ictericodes* Hering, and *Ictericodes* Lw. The weight of this character is very low.

Glans of aedeagus large (plesiomorphy), without sclerotized apicodorsal rod (apomorphic), with simple tubular acrophallus (apomorphy); scape of aedeagus without additional lobe (= ligula; Korneyev, 1985) (apomorphy). The aedeagus with large glans, sclerotized apicodorsal rod, 2(-3) semitubular sclerites of acrophallus and preapical lobe of the scape is common in Acanthonevrinae, Trypetinae: Gastrozonini and Tephritinae: Terelliini. These states characters are plesiomorphic. Xyphosiini, Acrotaeniini and the rest of Tephritinae possess advanced states of aedeagus characters (except the size of glans various) and are presumed to be the main monophyletic stem of Tephritinae opposite to Terelliini.

Aculeus apex blunt, rounded and broad (plesiomorphy). The blunt apex of aculeus is known for many Acanthonevrinae, Phytalmiinae, laying eggs into decaying wood and plant matter, and in Trypetinae: Gastrozonini, one of the most primitive feeders of living plant tissues. Terelliini, Xyphosiini, and Acrotaeniini also possess blunt aculeus that obviously cannot pierce plant tissues, and use it for oviposition between florets in composite flowerheads. This state of character is obviously plesiomorphic in Tephritinae, whereas the acute piercing ovipositors in the remaining tribes of this subfamily is of an apomorphic state, though probably liable to homoplasy.

Larvae of *Plioreocepta*, all Terelliini, *Xyphosia* and *Stenopa* (Tephritinae) have the reticulate pattern of the "facial mask" well-developed and similar in details; *Jamesomyia* and *Procecidochares* also have reticulate pattern, but no details are known. It has not been described for other Tephritinae, and is absent at least in *Urophora*. Such pattern is presumed a synapomorphy of *Plioreocepta* and Tephritinae, secondary reduced in larvae of advanced plant-feeding species. It is the symplesiomorphy of Tephritinae and does not show close relationships between Xyphosiini and other taxa of the subfamily.

Figs 1-13. *Ictericodes seriata* (1,4,7,9), *Orotava cribrata* (2,5,8,12) and *Merzomyia licenti* (3,6,11,13), male (1-8) and female (9-13) terminalia (1-3 — glans of aedeagus, 4-6 — epandrium, 7-8 — basiphallus, right view; 9-11 — aculeus, ventral view (a — apex, enlarged), 12-13 — spermatheca).

Рис. 1-13. *Ictericodes seriata* (1,4,7,9), *Orotava cribrata* (2,5,8,12) и *Merzomyia licenti* (3,6,11,13), терминалии самца (1-8) и самки (9-13) (1-3 — гланс эдеагуса, 4-6 — эпандрий, 7-8 — базифалл, вид справа; 9-11 — лезвие яйцеклада (а — вершина, увеличено), 12-13 — сперматека).

The diagnosis includes mostly plesiomorphic characters, but at least uniformly yellow (neither white, nor black) bristles (including posterior ocellar, all postocular, posterior notopleural, and anepimeral bristles), and the reticulate wing pattern are considered herein to be the synapomorphy. Palearctic *Xyphosia* and *Ictericodes*, as well as Nearctic *Ictericodes*, fit here. The New World genera of Acrotaeniini [Foote et al., 1993] are close to them in many characters, including peculiar similarities of spermathecae and aculeus shape. The only sufficient difference is mostly striate, not reticulate wing pattern; this character is of low value.

Hereof the three latter Holarctic genera are considered to belong to the same tribe, and closely related to the New World genera assigned to the Acrotaeniini, derived or sister group of Xyphosiini.

[*Ictericodes* Loew, 1873]

REMARKS. This generic name was misapplied to some Palearctic species now transferred in *Ictericodes* Hering, *Pseudacinia* Korneyev, and *Merzomyia* Korneyev, nom.n. It was treated among the "unplaced Tephritinae" by Foote et al. [1993]. The two Nearctic species, *Ictericodes seriata* (Lw.) and *I. circinata* (Lw.) possess all the diagnostic characters of the Xyphosiini,

including genital structures (Figs 1,4,7,9). See also remarks under *Merzomyia* below.

Ictericodes depuncta (Hering), **comb.n.**

Hering, 1936: 184 (*Ictericodes*); Chen in: Zia, Chen, 1938: 107 (*Acinia depunctata*, error); Foote, 1984: 70 (*Acinia*)

MATERIAL EXAMINED. Khabarovskiy Kray: Khabarovsk, 16.07.1931, ♂ (Pereleshina); Primorskiy Kray: Kamenushka, 28.07.1983, ♀ (Shatalkin), Spassk, 15.07.1961, ♀ (Zhelokhovtsev), Kedrovaya Pad', 25.08.1980, ♀ (Shatalkin).

DISTRIBUTION. Far East of Russia (new record), China (vicinities of Harbin).

Tribe Tephritini

Group of genera allied to *Sphenella*

REMARKS. This group belongs to Tephritini. Monophyly of the Old World *Sphenella* group of genera is supported by their strict association with host plants of the tribe Senecioneae and the number of frontal bristles reduced to two. Other traits of the group are the very characteristic structure of aedeagus, the presence of extremely or moderately long posterior prongs, associated with the flanges of epandrium in most genera,

Figs 14-17. *Tephritis*. Wings. 14 — *T. cometa cingulata* Hering; 15 — *T. sp. cf. trypaneina* Hering; 15-16 — *T. majuscula* Hering et Ito, two extreme variants of wing pattern.

Рис. 14-17. *Tephritis*. Крылья. 14 — *T. cometa cingulata* Hering; 15 — *T. sp. cf. trypaneina* Hering; 15-16 — *T. majuscula* Hering et Ito, два крайних варианта крылового рисунка.

assigned to this group by Munro [1957], Freidberg [1987] and Freidberg and Hancock [1989]. One more Afrotropical genus, namely *Parafeutreta* Munro, possessing all the essential characters of the group, was omitted from these works. Recently, Freidberg and Kaplan [1992] placed this genus in the *Sphenella* group. It is close to *Paratephritis* Shiraki. Phylogeny and classification of the group need further analysis.

Merzomyia Korneyev **nom.n.**

Westermannia Lioy, 1864 (Diptera), nom. praecoc. Hübner, 1821 (Lepidoptera). Type-species (by monotypy): *Westermannia tephritisoides* Lioy, 1864 (= *Trypeta westermanni* Meigen, 1826). — *Ictericia* sensu Hendel, 1927, non Coquillett, 1910, non Hendel, 1914. Type-species (by consequent invalid designation (Hendel, 1927)): *Trypeta westermanni* Meigen, 1826 (Palaeartic). — *Orotava* Frey: Korneyev, 1990 (pro parte).

DIAGNOSIS. Yellow-brown flies of moderate size, with dark brown wings with numerous irregular yellow dots and few hyaline spots on them. Eyes uniformly green in living specimens. Head slightly higher than, or as high as long; arista short pubescent; 2 fr, 2 or, posterior-or white; postorbital row with intermixed 4-8 long white bristles and 10-12 short black bristles; labellum longer than 0.7 of parastomal cavity length. Thorax sparsely microtomentose, subshining including scutum and scutellum; mesonotal setae white and moderately dense, not forming pattern of setulose and bare areas. Chaetotaxy complete; bristles brown to black, including p npl, except anepm white; dc between asa level and transverse suture; 4 scut. Wing elongate; 2 costal spurs 3 times longer than surrounding setae; vein R_{4+5} setulose to R-M above and below; lower squama slightly longer than upper one. Hindfemora without

anteroventral row of bristles, at most, with 6-7 smaller subapical. Abdominal terga very sparsely microtomentose, white setulose at most in posteriorly, black setulose in anteriorly. Female tergum 6 shorter than tergum 5. Male terminalia: epandrium wide, with flanges serrate and no prong-like lobes above them; aedeagus with rather long tube of acrophallus and reduced tale-like posterior extension of the glans (flagellum) (Fig. 3). Female terminalia: sytergosternum 7 fine brown or yellow setulose; aculeus rather broad, very gradually pointed apically, with subapical step and rounded apex; two round spermathecae without papillae.

REMARKS. The European *Trypeta westermanni* Mg. was placed by Loew [1862] into *Oxyphora* R.-D., 1830 (now treated as possible junior synonym of *Oxyina* R.-D.). Later, when Loew established *Ictericia* [Loew, 1873], for two Nearctic species, he noted, that "it will appear more natural to withdraw *O[xyphora] westermanni* from the genus [*Oxyphora*] and to form a new genus for it, together with the above described [*Trypeta seriata* Lw., 1862] ... This genus may be called *Ictericia*." Therefore, he originally included *Trypeta westermanni* into *Ictericia*.

Coquillett [1910] has designated the Nearctic *Trypeta seriata* Lw. as a type-species of *Ictericia* Lw. This designation was accepted by Hendel [1914] in the key to the of fruit-fly genera of the World. Nevertheless, later Hendel [1927] has erroneously designated the Palaeartic *Trypeta westermanni* Mg. as the type-species of *Ictericia*; and it was noted already by Foote and Freidberg [1981].

Recently, all Palaeartic species assigned to *Ictericia* were withdrawn from it and placed into *Orotava* Frey [Korneyev, 1990]. Dr. Bernhard Merz (Zürich) has

found that these species have isolated position and are not congeneric with the type species of *Orotava* (personal communication). In a further cladistic analysis (Norbom, Korneyev, *in preparation*) these species were shown to be a monophyletic group, corresponding to the genus *Westermannia* Liou, and not closely related to either *Orotava* or other genera of the *Sphenella* group. As the name of this genus is preoccupied, a new name is being established here.

ETYMOLOGY. This genus is named after Dr. Bernhard Merz in recognition of his contribution to the systematics of European Tephritinae. The generic name is derived from his name, and Greek *muia* (fly). The gender is feminine.

RELATIONSHIPS. This genus belongs to the *Sphenella* group of genera, fitting the diagnosis in the following autapomorphic characters: labella moderately elongate rather than capitate, epandrium broadened ventrally in posterior view, and larvae associated with plants from the genus *Senecio* s.lat. or closely related to it. *Merzomyia* is considered to be the sister-group to the remaining genera, because of having no additional synapomorphies with any other genera of the group and lacking characteristic *Sphenella*-like structure of aedeagus (with the short semitubular paired sclerites of acrophallus, evolving basal portion of ejaculatory duct, therefore extending beyond their apices as a membranous tube). The latter character is presumed to be the synapomorphy of the remaining genera, also secondarily modified in *Orotava* Frey, *Orthocanthoides* Freidberg, *Pseudophorellia* Freidberg & Hancock and in some species of *Telaletes* Munro. *Merzomyia* may also be considered a rather derived member, than the sister-group, because there is no sufficient evidence, that its acrophallus structure cannot be derived from the *Sphenella*-like one. Autapomorphies of *Merzomyia* are the following: abdominal terga (at least 2-4) black setulose anteriorly, acrophallus simple, elongate tubular, completely sclerotized, tail-like dorso-caudal flagellum reduced, papillae on spermathecae completely lacking.

Merzomyia fits near diagnosis of *Parafreutreta* in the following features: wing pattern mostly dark brown with yellow dots and few hyaline spots, no hyaline bands or wedges, R_{4+5} setulose above beyond **R-M** vein, hindfemora without anteroventral row of bristles, surstyli with serrate flanges, but without prong-like posteriorly directed process, differing in body colour yellow rather than brown, wing conspicuously elongate, and in all the characters listed above as its autapomorphies.

Orotava Frey resembles *Merzomyia* in the wing pattern mostly dark reticulate, the anteroventral row of bristles on hindfemora lacking, surstyli without prong-like process and aculeus with subapical steps, differing in all postorbitals black, R_{4+5} bare, wing pattern with more or less distinct subapical crossband composed of confluent hyaline spots, different structure of aedeagus and elongate and papillose spermathecae.

Ictericia Loew shares with *Merzomyia* the yellow body color, elongate brownish wing with yellow confluent dots and R_{4+5} vein setulose above and below at least to **R-M** crossvein. It differs well in the following characters: all the bristles, including posterior or, longer postorbital and anepimeral bristles, and all small setae yellow, **dc** in line with **asa**, epandrium not broadened ventrally, flanges lacking or, if present, never serrate, aculeus without subapical steps, spermathecae moder-

ately elongate, densely papillose; larvae in flowerheads of *Bidens* spp. (tribe Coreopsidae). From these characters I consider *Ictericia* to be a member of the tribe Xyphosiini (Tephritinae), not Tephritini.

SPECIES INCLUDED. *Merzomyia westermanni* (Meigen) **comb.n.** (= *Trypeta westermanni* Meigen, 1826) from southern Europe, *Merzomyia licenti* (Chen) **comb.n.** (= *Acinia licenti* Chen in: Zia and Chen, 1938) from China and Russian Far East, and *Merzomyia mongolica* (Korneyev) **comb.n.** (= *Orotava mongolica* Korneyev, 1990) from central Mongolia.

Group of genera allied to *Campiglossa*

Dioxyina bidentis (R.-D.)

Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830: 755 (*Stylia*); Foote, 1984: 113 (*Paroxyina*); White, 1988: 49; Korneyev, 1990: 428 (*Dioxyina*). — *cheni* Zia, 1937: 205; Foote, 1984: 113 (*Paroxyina*) **syn.n.**

MATERIAL EXAMINED. CHINA: ♂ (specimen labeled in Chinese), 12.06.1935, (name of collector in Chinese), "*Paroxyina cheni* Zia" [det. ? Y.Zia] (NHML).

According to Zia, *P. cheni* was described from a female specimen deposited in collection of "Agricultural Dept. of Nanking University". It was not available for examination. Nevertheless both original description and the specimen from China mentioned above show that *P. cheni* does not differ from *D. bidentis* and I treat them as synonyms.

Homoeotricha atrata (Wang) **comb.n.**

Wang, 1990: 296, 303 (*Gonioxyina*).

This species possesses all the characters of *Homoeotricha* Hering, as defined by Korneyev [1993], including wing pattern, head and wing shape and especially the extremely long labella. It fits very close to *H. arisanica* (Shiraki) from Taiwan and *H. procusa* (Dirlbek, Dirlbekova) from Mongolia, differing mainly in the presence of additional sausage-like hyaline spot just behind the stigmal apex. It was described from a single male from the Inner Mongolia. The three species are extremely similar, but synonymization is pending until additional materials are available.

Campiglossa luxorientis (Hering)

oxyinoides Hering, 1936: 186 (*Paroxyina*) (nom. praecoc., non *Paroxyina oxyinoides* (Bezzi, 1924). — *luxorientis* Hering, 1940: 16 (nom.n. pro *P. oxyinoides* Hering, 1936); Korneyev, 1986: 47 (*Paroxyina*); Korneyev, 1990: 454. — *melanochroa* Hering, 1941: 30 (*Paroxyina*) **syn.n.**

TYPE MATERIAL. *P. melanochroa*: HOLOTYPE: ♀: CHINA "Type" (red-boarded circle), "Type" (red paper square), "Charbin, Mandchukuo, 18.09.1940 W.Alin", "*Paroxyina melanochroa* m. M.Hering det. Holotype" (NHML). Non-type Material. Primorskiy Krai: Yakovlevka, ex *Heteropappus hispidus*, 16.09-23.10.1986, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀ (Zerova) (SIZK).

The holotype of *P. melanochroa* exhibits melanistic autumnal form of *P. luxorientis* mentioned by Korneyev [1990: 455]. Some specimens from *Heteropappus* have intermediate wing pattern and body coloration.

Group of genera allied to *Tephritis*

Tephritis Latreille, 1804

REMARKS. More than 30 species of this genus have already been recorded from eastern China, Korea, Japan,

Figs 18-27. *Tephritis*. Wings. 18 — *T. sonchina* Hering; 19 — *T. jocaste* Hering; 20 — *T. shansiana* Chen; 21 — *T. sinensis* Chen; 22 — *T. okera* Shinji; 23 — *T. pterostigma* Chen; 24 — *T. consimilis* Chen; 25 — *T. sp. cf. pterostigma* Chen; 27 — *T. multiguttata* Hering, 27 — *T. koreacola* Kwon (18,22,25 — original; 19,26 — redrawn from Hering, 1953, 20,21,23,24 — from Zia and Chen, 1938, 27 — from Kwon, 1985).

Рис. 18-27. *Tephritis*. Крылья. 18 — *T. sonchina* Hering; 19 — *T. jocaste* Hering; 20 — *T. shansiana* Chen; 21 — *T. sinensis* Chen; 22 — *T. okera* Shinji; 23 — *T. pterostigma* Chen; 24 — *T. consimilis* Chen; 25 — *T. sp. cf. pterostigma* Chen; 26 — *T. multiguttata* Hering, 27 — *T. koreacola* Kwon (18,22,25 — ориг.; 19,26 — по Hering, 1953, 20,21,23,24 — по Zia and Chen, 1938, 27 — по Kwon, 1985).

and the Russian Far East, and approximately a dozen of species are known to occur in the bordering regions of western and central China, Mongolia and Siberia. The systematics of the European species of *Tephritis* were rather confused until recently, and a provisional review of East Palaearctic species shows, that more than one

third of specific names are possible synonyms. No comprehensive keys exist, and many species are not recognizable from their original descriptions. Therefore, a complete revision of the Far East species of *Tephritis*, involving the examination of all known type specimens, is necessary, but I suppose that the preliminary revision-

ary data given below add more to the knowledge of this genus.

Merz [1992] recognized species groups in the genus; during the present study, several species were found to have very similar structure of female terminalia and host-plant associations, despite of differences in wing pattern that had been previously used as a main taxonomic character. Thus, the species of the Far East are arranged into the species groups below.

Group of species related to *Tephritis dilacerata*

DIAGNOSIS. Wing pattern: cell R_1 with 3 hyaline spots; cell sc with hyaline or yellow spot; crossvein $R-M$ with 2-4 hyaline dots or hyaline area around it; tergosternum 7 with very few white setae above; aculeus rather short, weakly sclerotized, except dorso-basal portion, somewhat blunt apically, without subapical steps (Fig. 30). Larvae in flowerheads of *Sonchus* spp. (Lactuceae).

The following species are included: *T. dilacerata* Lw. (Europe to Kazakhstan), *T. formosa* Lw. (Europe), *T. kovalevi* Korneyev & Kameneva (Central Asia: Tien-Shang), and *T. sonchina* Hering (the Far East).

Tephritis sonchina Hering Figs 18, 30.

Hering, 1937: 112; Foote, 1984: 133. — *mandschurica* Hering, 1953: 12; Foote, 1984: 131, *syn.n.* — *alini* Hering, 1936: 188; Foote, 1984: 127, *possible senior synonym.*

MATERIAL EXAMINED. *T. sonchina*: SYNTYPES: ♂, ♀: CHINA: "Charbin, 1936", "*Tephritis sonchina* m. det. M.Hering 1937" and "Typus" (red paper square) (DEI) (syntypes of this series are also located in Zoologische Staatssammlung, München and in NHML, but were not studied). *T. mandschurica*: HOLOTYPE: ♂: CHINA: "Type" (on red-boarded circle), "Type" (on red paper square), "Charbin, Mandschurien, 11-17. VII. 1951 (W.Alin), "*Tephritis mandschurica* m. det. M.Hering 1951 Holotype" (MNHL).

Non-type materials: RUSSIA: Amurskaya oblast, ♂: Klimoutsy, 20.05.1959, (Borisova) (ZISP); Primorskiy Kray, ♂, ♀: Kamenushka, 4.08.1984, 16.09.1987, (Shatalkin); ♂, *ibid.*, 24.10.1968, (Gorodkov); ♀, Kamen'-Rybolov, 5.09.1978, (Kasparyan) (ZISP). CHINA: ♂ "Chandaochenzy [Mandschuria], 6.07.1954", (Alin) (NHML).

REMARKS. All the examined specimens have very similar wing pattern, resembling that of *T. crepidis* Hendel (Fig. 18) (in the West Palaearctic species of the *dilacerata* group apical brown dots are isolated and do not form the apical fork). *T. alini* was described from a male specimen (not examined), that was said to have the wing pattern also very similar to *T. crepidis*, and scutellum reddish brown, that fits well *T. sonchina* too. As this species was described from a male, it cannot be securely identified and placed in the *dilacerata* group until the Far East fauna will be completely examined. Thus, in the meantime I prefer to treat the two as separate species.

Group of species related to *Tephritis cometa*

DIAGNOSIS. Wing pattern: cell R_1 with 3 hyaline spots; cell sc without hyaline or yellow spot; crossvein $R-M$ with 2-4 hyaline dots or hyaline area around it, or without; tergosternum 7 with numerous white setae above in basal half; aculeus sclerotized, long, slightly contracted subapically, sharply pointed apically, with-

out subapical steps or apical incision (Figs 28, 29). Larvae in flowerheads of *Cirsium* spp. (Cardueae).

The following taxa are included: *T. cometa* Lw. (Europe to Kazakhstan), *T. cometa cingulata* Hering (The Far East), *T. cometa israelis* Freidberg (Israel), and *T. majuscula* Hering & Ito (The Far East). *Trypeta koreacola* Kwon is also associated with *Cirsium* sp. and said to be very close to *T. majuscula* [Kwon, 1985: 91]. This species has wing pattern more similar to *T. femoralis* Chen and *T. jocaste* Hering, and therefore, may belong elsewhere; female terminalia were not examined. No other species associated with Asteraceae-Cardueae were found to be closely related.

Tephritis cometa cingulata Hering Figs 14, 29.

Hering, 1936: 189; Richter, 1975: 596; Foote, 1984: 128.

MATERIAL EXAMINED. Amurskaya oblast: Klimoutsy, 21.05.1958, ♀ (Borisova) (ZISP); Khabarovskiy Kray: Dormidontovka, 92 km S from Khabarovsk, 28.07.1978, ♀ (Kasparyan) (ZISP); Primorskiy Kray: Kamenushka ("Suputinskiy zapovednik"), 24.10.1968, 14, 27.07.1983, 25.07, 4.08.1984, 14, 21.10.1987, 4 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀ (Gorodkov; Shatalkin; Antropov) (ZISP; ZMUM).

REMARKS. Differs from the nominative subspecies in having the well-developed yellow pattern behind the stigma (Fig. 14) and longer ovipositor (Fig. 28). Previously recorded only from China (vicinity of Harbin) and Mongolia (South Gobi). The latter record apparently needs further confirmation. Freidberg (pers. comm.) suggests that *T. cometa israelis* Freidberg apparently might be a junior synonym of *T. cometa cingulata*.

Tephritis majuscula Hering et Ito Figs 16, 17, 28.

Hering & Ito, 1953: 1; Foote, 1984: 131; Ito, 1984: 246.

Material. S. Sakhalin: Pravda, S of Kholmok, 26. 05. 1968, ♂ (Nartshuk), 25.05.1973, 8 ♂♂, ♀ (Ermolenko, Kerzhner); Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk, 13.06.1954, 10, 18.07.1955, 12.07.1956, 3 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀ (Violovitsh), Novoaleksandrovsk, 28.06.1973, ♂ (Kerzhner) (ZISP), *ibid.*, 17.20.06, 7.31.07.1986, 3 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀ (Nesterov) (SIZK); S. Kuril: Urup: Podgornoye, 8.08.1963, ♀ (Azarova); Shikotan: Malokurilsk, Krabozavodskoye and Tserkovnaya bay, 23.06.1968, 20-21.06, 16-20.08.1973, 18.08.1971, 22.09.1968, 24 ♂♂, 19 ♀♀ (Kerzhner, Nartshuk, Gorodkov); Kunashir: Tretyakovo, Alekhino, Mendeleyevo, Golovnin volcano, Sernovodsk, Dubovoye, 2-3.06.1963, 2 ♂♂, 5-6.09.1971, 2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀ (Tanasichuk, Nartshuk), 12.06-1.09.1973, 14 ♂♂, 14 ♀♀ (Kasparyan, Kerzhner) (ZISP); Stolbchatyi cape, 9.07.1985, 2 ♂♂ (Churkin) (ZMUM).

REMARKS. The wing pattern is rather variable, having a hyaline dot or spot in cell R_{2+3} basad of the $R-M$ level in some specimens (Fig. 16). Previously recorded only from Japan. Host plants: *Cirsium norikuraensis* Nakai, *C. spicatum* (Maxim.) Matsum., *Cirsium* spp. [Ito, 1984].

Group of species related to *Tephritis leontodontis*

DIAGNOSIS. Wing pattern: cell R_1 with 3 (in some specimens only 2) hyaline spots; cell sc with or without hyaline spot; crossvein $R-M$ with or without 2-4 hyaline dots or hyaline area around it; tergosternum 7 with few white setae above; aculeus sclerotized, moderately long, neither contracted subapically, nor sharply pointed

Figs 28-37. *Tephritis*. Aculei (28-35) and spermathecae (36-37). 28 — *T. majuscula* Hering et Ito; 29 — *T. cometa cingulata* Hering; 30 — *T. sonchina* Hering; 31 — *T. okera* Shinji; 32 — *T. dioscurea* Lw. (Kunashir); 33 — *T. sp. cf. sinensis* Chen; 34 — *T. sp. cf. pterostigma* Chen; 35-36 — *T. jocaste* Hering; 37 — *T. trypaneina* Hering.

Рис. 28-37. *Tephritis*. Лезвия яйцекладов (28-35) и сперматеки (36-37). 28 — *T. majuscula* Hering et Ito; 29 — *T. cometa cingulata* Hering; 30 — *T. sonchina* Hering; 31 — *T. okera* Shinji; 32 — *T. dioscurea* Lw. (Кунашир); 33 — *T. sp. cf. sinensis* Chen; 34 — *T. sp. cf. pterostigma* Chen; 35-36 — *T. jocaste* Hering; 37 — *T. sp. cf. trypaneina* Hering.

apically, without subapical steps, but with conspicuous, very deep apical incision (Fig. 31). Host plants: *Leontodon*, *Picris* and *Atractylodes* spp. (Lactuceae).

The following species are included: *T. leontodontis* Degeer, *T. truncata* Lw., *T. fallax* Lw., *T. mariannae* Merz (all from Europe), and *T. okera* Shinji (Japan, the Far East Russia).

Tephritis okera (Shinji)

Figs 22, 31.

Shinji, 1940: 2 (*Platensia* [sic!]; Ito, 1947: 60, **sp. resurr.** — *ismene* Hering, 1953: 14; Foote, 1984: 130, **syn.n.** — *separata*: Ito, 1984: 248 (misidentification), non Rondani, 1871.

MATERIAL EXAMINED. *T. ismene*: HOLOTYPE: ♂: CHINA: "Type" (red-boarded paper circle), "Type" (red paper square), "Tigrovaja Padj/ Manschurei/ 19.VIII.1951 W.Alin", "*Tephritis ismene* m. Type ♂ / det. M.Hering 1951"; PARATYPES: ♀: "Allotype" (red paper square) and ♂: "Paratype" (red paper square), other labels as in the holotype (NHML).

Non-type Material. JAPAN: Honshu, Nagano, Yatsugatake, 1260 m height, on *Artemisia*, 11.08.1949, 2 ♀♀ (Ito) ("*Tephritis separata* Rondani, 1871 Det. S.Ito, 1957) (UPO). RUSSIA: Khabarovskiy Krai: Sobolevo, 20 km S of Viazemski, 29.07.1978, ♂, 2 ♀ (Kasparyan) (ZISP); Primorskiy Krai: Gorno-Tayozhnaya Stanysiya, 31.08.1978, ♂ (Kasparyan) (ZISP), *ibid.*, ex *Picris koreana*, 5.09-12.11.1987, ♀ (Zerova) (SIZK); Kamenushka, 2.08.1984, ♂, 21-22.09.1987, 4 ♂♂, ♀ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM), *ibid.*, 18.08.1987, ♂ (Kostjukov) (SIZK); Vladivostok, "valley of the Suputinka river", 3.08.1963 (Nartshuk); Khasan distr., Narva spring SW of Barabash, 4.08.1978, ♀ (Kasparyan) (ZISP); S-Kuriles: Kunashir: Tretyakovo, Sernovodsk, 12.06.1968, 16.06-10.08.1973, ♂, 6 ♀♀ (Nartshuk, Kerzhner, Kasparyan) (ZISP), Stolbchatyi cape, 29.06.1985, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀ (Churkin) (ZMUM).

REMARKS. I have not found any conspicuous differences between the type specimens of *T. ismene*, and *T. cf. separata* from Ito's collection, and *T. okera* specimens redescribed by Ito, so I consider them to be conspecific. Moreover, the true *T. separata* Rd. from Europe, recently redescribed by Merz [1992] has the tergal ratio of tergosternum 7 1.5 times longer than in *T. okera*, and different shape of aculeus apex. In this respect I cannot consider this species to be a senior synonym of *T. okera*, and resurrect the latter from synonymy. *T. okera* has the aculeus apex deeply incised apically, as in *T. mariannae* Merz which is associated with *Leontodon hispidus* in Switzerland. It somewhat differs from the latter species in the wing pattern by lacking the hyaline spot in pterostigma (except one female from Kunashir) and by some other details. A few specimens of *T. okera* do not differ from *T. mariannae* conspicuously, and further study is required to clarify the relationships between these species.

Group of species related to *Tephritis separata*

DIAGNOSIS. Wing pattern: cell R_1 with 3 hyaline spots; cell **sc** with or without hyaline spot; crossvein **R-M** with or without 2-4 hyaline dots or hyaline area around it; tergosternum 7 with few white setae above; aculeus sclerotized, moderately long, neither contracted subapically, nor sharply pointed, but narrowed apically, without subapical steps, but with conspicuous, but not deep apical incision (Fig. 33). Host plants: *Leontodon* and *Picris* spp. (Lactuceae).

The following species are included: *T. separata* Rond., *T. divisa* Rond., and *T. mutabilis* Merz (Europe).

Tephritis sp. cf. *sinensis* Chen

ramulosa Chen in: Zia et Chen, 1938: 159, nom. praecoc. — *sinensis* Chen, 1940: 11, nom.nov. *proramulosa* Chen, non Becker. MATERIAL EXAMINED. Amurskaya oblast: Klimoutsy, 24.05, 27.09.1958, ♂, ♀ (G.Zinovjev) (ZISP).

REMARKS. This species corresponds to the description of *T. ramulosa* Chen, and also fits the description and figures of European *T. separata* Rond. The available material is too meagre to identify this species, and at most it may be considered to belong to this group.

Group of species related to *Tephritis pterostigma*

DIAGNOSIS. Wing pattern: cell R_1 with 3 (in some specimens only 2) hyaline spots; cell **sc** without hyaline or yellow spot, very often with basal hyaline incision; crossvein **R-M** never with 2-4 hyaline dots or hyaline area around it; tergosternum 7 with numerous white setae above in basal 1/2-2/3; aculeus sclerotized, moderately long, neither constricted subapically, nor sharply pointed apically, without subapical steps, but with shallow apical incision (Figs 34, 35). Host plants unknown.

The following taxa are included: *T. pterostigma* Chen (China, the Russian Far East), *T. femoralis* Chen (the Far East), *T. bipartita* Hendel (China: Kiangsu), *T. triangula* Ito (Japan), *T. jocaste* Hering (the Far East), *T. koreacola* Kwon (Korea), and *T. heringi* nom.n. (south eastern China).

Tephritis heringi Korneyev nom.n.

multiguttata Hering, 1953: 14; Hardy, 1977: 131, non Becker, 1913 (*Euribia*).

REMARKS. Hering overlooked homonymy of this species, described after two males from south eastern China with the species described by Becker from Iran and transferred into *Tephritis* by Hendel [1927].

Tephritis sp. cf. *pterostigma* Chen

MATERIAL EXAMINED. Amurskaya oblast: Korsakovo, 100 km W of Svobodnyi, 14.20.09.1958, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, *ibid.*, Samodan peninsula, 4.08.1959, ♂ (G.Zinovjev); Simonovo, 29-30.05, 4.8-9.06.1959, 18-21.09.1958, 10 ♂♂, 8 ♀♀ (Kerzhner, G.Zinovjev); Klimoutsy, 26.05, 2-23.06, 24-27.09.1958 (G.Zinovjev, Borisova) (ZISP); Primorskiy Krai: Kamenushka ("*Suputinskiy zapovednik*"), 24.10.1968, ♂ (Gorodkov); Vladivostok, Sedanka, 27.10.1978, ♀ (Gorodkov); Khasan distr., Andreyevka, 8.08.1978, ♀ (Kasparyan) (ZISP); Ryazanovka, 9.06.1989, ♀ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM).

REMARKS. The specimens listed above share the possession of additional third hyaline spot in cell R_1 , and distinctive pale brown grid pattern covering more than 2/3 of cell cua_1 and extending into the anal lobe (Fig. 25), and also in having the tergosternum 7 moderately long, densely covered with white setae on its basal half, and in the aculeus slightly flattened, with the subapical steps and shallow apical incision (Fig. 34). *T. pterostigma* (Fig. 23), *T. consimilis* Chen (Fig. 24), *T. bipartita* Hendel, *T. triangula* Ito, *T. heringi* Korneyev and possibly *T. koreacola* Kwon (Fig. 27) fit here well, differing in minute details of the wing patterns. None of the type specimens of these species were available for study; female terminalia not dissected; moreover, *T. heringi* was described from the males.

All these names mentioned above may belong either to one species or to the group of closely related species,

and I am unable to resolve the problem of this extremely confused possible synonymy.

Tephritis jocaste Hering

Hering, 1953: 11; Foote, 1984: 130. — *femoralis* Chen in: Zia et Chen, 1938: 155; Foote, 1984: 130, and *shansiana* Chen, 1940: 529, possible senior synonyms.

MATERIAL EXAMINED. Primorskiy Krai: Gorno-Tayozhnaya Stantsiya SW of Ussuriysk, 2.08.1963, ♂, ♀ (Nartshuk), Kamenushka ("Suputinskiy zapovednik"), 24.10.1962, 2 ♂♂ (Gorodkov) (ZISP), ibid., 25.08.1984, ♀ (Shatalkin), Khasan town, Doritseni lake, 22.10.1968, ♂, 2 ♀♀, Kedrovaya Pad', 18.10.1968, ♀ (Gorodkov) (ZISP); Khasan distr., Tsukanovo, 17.07.1989, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀ (Churkin).

REMARKS. The specimens listed above share the possession two hyaline spots in cell R_1 (Fig. 19), ovipositor with tergosternum 7 densely white setulose and aculeus more or less conspicuously angulate in apical third (Fig. 35). Abdominal coloration varies from broadly yellow to completely black, wing pattern sometimes with yellow dots, or completely dark brown with hyaline spots. *T. femoralis* and *T. shansiana* fit well some variants of the wing pattern and body coloration in the series from the Russian Far East, but aculeus shape was not examined in the specimens from Ordos, Kansu, and Shansi. Therefore, I consider these species only as possible senior synonyms of *T. jocaste*.

Group of species related to *Tephritis angustipennis*

DIAGNOSIS. Wing pattern: cell R_1 with 2 hyaline spots; cell sc without hyaline or yellow spot; crossvein $R-M$ with or without hyaline dots or hyaline area around it (Fig. 32); tergosternum 7 with numerous white setae above in basal 1/2-2/3; aculeus sclerotized, moderately short, neither contracted subapically, without subapical steps or apical incision (Fig. 32). Host plants: *Ptarmica*, *Tanacetum*, and *Artemisia* spp. (Anthemideae).

The following taxa are included: *T. angustipennis* Lw. (Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, the Russian Far East: ? Kamchatka, northern North America), *T. dioscorea* Lw. (Europe, Kazakhstan, the Russian Far East, Japan), *T. nigricauda* Lw. (Europe, ? Syria, ? Afghanistan, ? the Russian Far East), *T. brachyura brachyura* Lw. (Europe, ? Iran, ? China), *T. brachyura nigrofemorata* Hendel (western China), *T. variata* Beck. (Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, western China), *T. nebulosa* Beck. (China: eastern Tibet), *T. kukunoria* Hendel (western China), *T. trypaneina* Hering (the Far East: China and Russia), *T. carcassa* Dirlbek & Dirlbek (Korea), *T. bimaculata* Freidberg (Israel, Egypt), *T. dentatus* Wang (China: Inner Mongolia), *T. annuliformis* Wang (China: Inner Mongolia), *T. consutus* Wang (China: Inner Mongolia), and *T. calliopsis* Wang (China: Inner Mongolia). Most of the Far East species are unrecognizable, and at least 3 to 4 of these specific names might be junior synonyms of other ones from this group.

This group of species will be revised in a separate paper.

Species of unresolved position

Tephritis hyosciami L.

MATERIAL EXAMINED. Amurskaya oblast: Klimoutsy, 13.24.09.1958, 2 ♂♂ (G.Zinovjev) (ZISP).

An occasionally introduced species, previously recorded only from Europe. Associated with *Carduus* thistles.

Group of genera allied to *Trupanea*

This group is represented in the Palaearctic East Asia by some species of subcosmopolitan genus *Trupanea* Schrank (most of the New World species need re-examination of their generic position), and three more species of *Urelliosoma* (*Allocraspeda*) V.Richter and *Donara* V.Richter, the latter two are restricted to Transbaikalia, Mongolia, and China (Kansu).

Trupanea amoena (Frauenfeld)

MATERIAL EXAMINED. Amurskaya oblast: Klimoutsy, 9.09.1958, ♀ (G.Zinovjev); Primorskiy Krai: Vladivostok, "the Suputinka riv. valley", 3.08.1963, ♂ (Nartshuk) (ZISP).

Trupanea convergens Hering

MATERIAL EXAMINED. Amurskaya oblast: Simonovo, 11.06.12.07.1959, 2 ♀♀ (Kerzhner); Klimoutsy, 22.05, 8.23.06, 13.07.1959, 7 ♀♀ (G.Zinovjev, Borisova) (ZISP).

Trupanea sp.

MATERIAL EXAMINED. Amurskaya oblast: Simonovo, 8.07.1959, ♂ (Kerzhner), Klimoutsy, 16.07.1958 ♂ (G.Zinovjev) (ZISP).

Though these specimens have somewhat distinct wing pattern, they are apparently only the males of the previous species.

Trupanea guttistella Hering

Hering, 1951: 13; Foote, 1984: 137. — *collina* Ito, 1984: 255 syn.n.

MATERIAL EXAMINED. *T. guttistella*: HOLOTYPE: ♂: CHINA: "Type" (red boarded circle), "Type" (red paper square), "Charbin, Mandshurei, 11.IX.1949", "*Trypanea guttistella* m. det M.Hering 1950. Holotype"; PARATYPE: ♀: "Type" (red-boarded circle), "Type" (red paper square), ibid., 20.07.1945, "*Trypanea guttistella* m. det. M.Hering, 1950. Allotype" (NHML). *T. collina*: PARATYPES: ♂: JAPAN: Honsyu, Sinano: Siga-Koogen, 1600 m, on *Anaphalis*, 11.09.1953 (Ito) (red handwritten label (with ball-point pen): "Allotypoid *Trypanea collina* Ito", ♀: JAPAN: Tyubu-Gifu, Takayama, 25.07.1954 (Kodama) (with blank blue rectangle) (UIPO).

Non-type materials: RUSSIA: Primorskiy Krai: Kamenushka, 11.07.1984, 22.09.1987, ♂, ♀ (Shatalkin) (ZMUM), Vladivostok, on a window, 14.09.1968, 2 ♂♂, ♀ (Petrova), "the Lyanchikhe riv.", 20.06.1963, ♀ (Falkovich), Kedrovaya Pad', 24.06.1962, ♂ (Nartshuk) (ZISP); S-Kuriles: Kunashir: Mendeleyevo, 3.07.1973, ♂, Sernovodsk, 16.07.1973, Dubovoye nr. Golovnino, 18.22.07.1973, 3 ♀♀ (Kerzhner) (ZISP).

REMARKS. Wing patterns of both the mainland specimens and of the specimens from Kurile Islands are rather variable and also sexually dimorphic. Males are very similar to the type specimens of *T. guttistella* and females correspond to *T. collina*. The specimens from southern Primorskiy Krai more often have wing pattern with the hyaline spots between the rays in cell M (= Cp_2) partially or completely confluent, as it was figured in the monograph on Japanese tephritids [Ito, 1984: Figs 374-375].

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